

GENERAL LECTURE 2

A Model of the Curing Process of Epoxy Matrix Composites

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ABSTRACT

A model is described for simulating the process for curing epoxy matrix composites. The model relates the cure cycle (cure temperature, cure pressure, cure time) to the local temperature, viscosity, degree of cure of the resin, and the resin flow perpendicular to the fibers. The model also provides information regarding changes in void sizes during cure and the residual stresses in each ply after cure. The application of the model in the selection of the appropriate cure cycle and in controlling the cure process during manufacture is discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Components and structures made of composite materials are manufactured by forming the soft, uncured fiber-resin mixture into the desired shape, and then curing this mixture at preselected temperatures and pressures. The magnitudes and durations of the temperatures and pressures applied during the curing process (referred to as the cure cycle) significantly affect the performance of the finished product. Thick laminates especially may be affected by the cure cycle because of the variation of properties across the laminate.

Since the cure cycle has a marked effect upon the quality of the finished composite, it must be selected carefully for each application. Specifically, it is important to use cure cycles resulting in composites which a) are cured uniformly, b) have specified resin contents, c) have minimum void contents, and d) are cured in the shortest possible time. The cure cycle which meets these requirements can best be determined by the use of an analytic model. Such a model must relate the cure cycle to the thermal, chemical and physical processes occurring in the prepreg during cure. These processes may be characterized by parameters such as the instantaneous local temperature, viscosity, degree of cure of the resin, and the resin flow. An appropriate model should provide these parameters, as well as the void sizes and the residual stresses in the composite after cure. A model which yields these parameters is presented in this paper, in four parts:

- a) The "thermo-chemical model" gives the instantaneous, local temperatures, the degrees of cure, and the viscosity.
- b) The "flow model" provides the resin flow.
- c) The "void model" gives the sizes of voids.
- d) The "stress model" results in the residual stresses.

The information provided by the model has specific uses in the manufacturing process. First, it can be used to select the appropriate cure cycle for a specific application. Second, it may be utilized to control the cure temperature and cure pressure during manufacture. The model can also aid in the development of new resin systems by identifying those material properties which play important roles in the curing process.

THE CURING PROCESS

In this section a brief description is given of the main features of the curing process, with emphasis on those aspects which pertain to the formulation of the model.

The laminate, constructed of unidirectional prepreg tapes, is placed upon a metal "tool plate" (Fig. 1). An absorbent material (referred to as the "bleeder") is placed on one side (or on both sides) of the prepreg. Teflon and "peel" plies are placed on both sides of the prepreg to prevent sticking, as illustrated in Fig. 1. A metal plate is placed on top of the bleeder. An air breather is also added when curing is done in an autoclave. Restraints (called "dams") are mounted around the prepreg to prevent lateral motion and to minimize resin flow parallel to the tool plate and through the edges. A plastic sheet ("vacuum bag") is placed around the entire assembly when vacuum is applied during cure. Here, we are not concerned with the vacuum, as it has no direct effect on the model.

The cure process involves the application of heat and pressure. The applied heat increases the temperature in the prepreg. This increase in temperature initiates and maintains the chemical reactions required in the cure. The increase in temperature and the simultaneous changes in the molecular structure

Figure 1: Schematic of the prepreg lay up.

result in a decrease of the resin viscosity (enabling the resin to "flow" through the prepreg) and, at later times, in the high viscosities characteristic of the gelled material. The applied pressure provides the force needed to produce the resin flow and to squeeze excess resin out of the prepreg.

The applied temperature and pressure also affect the sizes of voids inside the prepreg by influencing the rates at which vapors are transported into or out of the voids. The temperature of the prepreg during cure also influences the residual stresses in the composite after the cure, as these stresses are proportional to the differences in temperatures in the material during and after the cure.

In summary, the applied cure cycle affects the following parameters of interest:

- a) the temperature inside the prepreg as a function of position and time,
- b) the degree of cure of the resin as a function of position and time,
- c) the resin viscosity as a function of position and time,
- d) the resin flow, the amount of resin in the prepreg, and the amount of resin in the bleeder as functions of position and time,
- e) the changes in the void sizes as functions of position and time, and
- f) the residual stresses in the composite as functions of position.

The problem at hand is to establish a model which provides these parameters for specified heat inputs and applied pressures. A model suitable for this purpose is described in the following sections. In order to emphasize the concepts and the solution methods, the model is presented for composites in which the properties vary only across the thickness (flat plate geometry). However, the model and the method are general and can be extended readily to complex geometries. Thus, we consider a fiber reinforced epoxy resin composite (thickness L) constructed of unidirectional continuous fiber prepreg tape (Fig. 2). A bleeder (thickness L_B) is placed on top of the prepreg. Initially, (time $t < 0$), the resin is uncured and the bleeder contains no resin. Starting at time $t = 0$ the system is exposed to a temperature T_0 . The cure temperatures T_0 may be the same or different on the two sides of the composite-bleeder-tool plate assembly. At some time t_p ($t_p > 0$) a known pressure P_0 is applied to the system, squeezing excess resin from the composite into the bleeder. The objective is to determine the parameters listed in points (a)-(f) above for specified cure temperatures and cure pressures, both of which may vary with time.

THERMO-CHEMICAL MODEL

The temperature distribution, the degree of cure of the resin, and the viscosity can be calculated using the law of conservation of energy (1-6). In the present problem, heat transfer through the prepreg by convection may be neglected. With this simplification, for the one dimensional geometry under consideration (i.e. the properties vary only perpendicular to the tool plate) the energy equation becomes

$$\frac{\partial \rho C T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial z} k \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} + \rho \dot{H}_r \quad (1)$$

where ρ and C are the density and specific heat of the material, k is the thermal conductivity perpendicular to the plate (z direction, Fig. 2) and T is the temperature. The term on the left hand side represents the rate of change of energy. The first and second terms on the right hand side represent the heat transfer by conduction and the heat generated by chemical reactions, respectively. \dot{H}_r is the heat generated by unit mass and is related to the degree of cure

Figure 2: Illustration of the model

of the resin α by the expression

$$\dot{H}_r = \frac{d\alpha}{dt} H_r \quad (2)$$

H_r is the total or ultimate heat of reaction during cure and $d\alpha/dt$ is the reaction or cure rate. The assumption is generally made that the rate of heat generation during cure is proportional to the rate of cure and that the degree of cure of the resin (denoted as the degree of cure α) may be written as (7-17)

$$\alpha = H(t)/H_r \quad (3)$$

$H(t)$ is the heat evolved from the beginning of the reaction to some intermediate time t . For an uncured material α is taken to be zero, while for a completely cured material α is unity. The parameter α was chosen as a measure of the progress of the cure process because it is a suitable indicator of the changes occurring on the molecular level. The degree of cure can be calculated once α is known at each instant of time

$$\alpha = \int_0^t \frac{d\alpha}{dt} dt \quad (4)$$

In order to complete the model the dependence of the cure rate on the temperature and on the degree of cure must be known. Numerous expressions have been proposed in the past for relating $d\alpha/dt$ to T and α (9-21). The expression most appropriate for the material under consideration should be employed in the calculations. The following is a typical expression for $d\alpha/dt$

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \left[A_1 \exp \left(\frac{-E_1}{RT} \right) + A_2 \exp \left(\frac{-E_2}{RT} \right) \alpha^m \right] (1 - \alpha)^n (B - \alpha) \quad (5)$$

A_1, A_2 are the Arrhenius pre-exponential factors, E_1, E_2 are Arrhenius activation energies, R is the gas constant, n, m and B are constants. Values of these constants, as well as the value of the heat of reaction H_r , can be determined experimentally by differential scanning calorimetry (7-20, 22). It is emphasized that any other suitable expression may be used to calculate $d\alpha/dt$.

The initial conditions corresponding to eqs. (1)-(5) are

$$\left. \begin{aligned} T &= T_i(z) \\ \alpha &= 0 \end{aligned} \right\} \begin{aligned} 0 &\leq z \leq L \\ t &< 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

The boundary conditions for eqs. (1)-(5) require that the temperature be specified on the top T_u and bottom T_L surfaces of the prepreg

$$\left. \begin{aligned} T &= T_L(t) \quad \text{at} \quad z = 0 \\ T &= T_u(t) \quad \text{at} \quad z = L \end{aligned} \right\} t \geq 0 \quad (7)$$

In general, T_L and T_u differ from the cure temperature T_0 because the temperature changes across the different materials surrounding the prepreg. T_L and T_u can be calculated from the known values of T_0 using the heat conduction equation. Details of these calculations are straightforward and, for the sake of brevity, are not included here.

Solutions to eqs. (2)-(7) yield the temperature T , the rate of cure $d\alpha/dt$, and the degree of cure α as functions of position and time inside the material. Once these parameters are known, the resin viscosity μ can be calculated from an appropriate empirical expression relating μ to both T and α (23-25). One form of such a relationship is

$$\ln \mu(T, t) = \ln \mu_{\infty} + \frac{E_{\mu}}{RT} + \int_0^t K_{\infty} \exp \left[-\frac{E_k}{RT} \right] dt \quad (8)$$

where μ_{∞} and K_{∞} are the initial viscosity and gelation pre-exponential factors respectively, and E_{μ} and E_k are the apparent activation energies for the initial viscosity and for gelation respectively. These constants can be determined by cone and plate viscometer measurements. Equation (8), or any other suitable expression may be used to calculate μ

FLOW MODEL

At some time t ($t > 0$) pressure is applied to the composite-bleeder system (Fig. 2). As a result of this pressure resin flows from the composite into the bleeder. The resin flow rate depends on a) the magnitude of the applied pressure P , b) the air pressure in the bleeder P_b , c) the viscosity of the resin in the composite and in the bleeder, d) the arrangement and volume fraction of fibers in the composite, e) the porosity of the bleeder and, f) the thicknesses of the composite and the bleeder.

Resin may flow in the directions normal and parallel to the tool plate. In practice the width and length of the composite are large compared to the thickness L . For this reason, and because of the restraining effects of the dams (and the vacuum bags) placed around the prepreg, resin flow along the plate is negligible. In fact, some resin flow through the edges does occur but, in general, the region affected by this lateral flow is small and is confined to the vicinity of the edges. Therefore, resin flow is considered here only in the direction normal to the tool plate.

Owing to the complex geometry, the equations describing the flow through the prepreg and the bleeder cannot be established exactly. Nevertheless, an approximate formulation of the problem is feasible. This formulation is based on the observation that both the bleeder and the prepreg resemble porous media. In the case of the bleeder this resemblance is evident. There is also a strong resemblance between the cross section of the prepreg and a porous medium, as illustrated by the photomicrograph in Fig. 3. These resemblances suggest that the flow through the prepreg and the bleeder may be approximated by expressions developed for flow through porous media. This approximation was made by Loos and Springer (6) in formulating their model of the resin flow. The Loos-Springer model is summarized below. The model assumes that inertia forces are negligible

Figure 3: Photomicrograph of an eight ply unidirectional composite after curing

compared to viscous forces and that, at any instant of time, the velocities in the prepreg and in the bleeder may be represented by Darcy's law (26)

$$v = - \frac{S}{\mu} \frac{dP}{dz} \quad (9)$$

S is the apparent permeability, μ is the viscosity, and dP/dz is the pressure gradient.

Before proceeding with the model the behavior of the prepreg plies during the squeezing action should be examined. As pressure is applied the first (top) ply ($n=1$, Fig. 4) moves toward the second ply ($n=2$), while resin is squeezed out from the space between the plies. This resin seeps through the fiber bundles of the first ply. When the fibers in the first ply get close to the fibers in the second ply, the two plies move together toward the third ply, squeezing the resin out of the space between the second and the third ply. This sequence of events is repeated for the subsequent plies. Thus, the interaction of the fibers proceeds down the prepreg in a wavelike manner (Fig. 4). Some compacting

Figure 4: Resin flow during cure pressure application

of the fibers within the individual plies may also occur, but as a first approximation, this effect is neglected here.

It is noted that there is a pressure drop only across those plies through which resin flow takes place. The pressure is constant (and is equal to the applied pressure P_o) across the rest of the prepreg.

The law of conservation of mass (together with eq. 9) gives the following expression for the rate of change of mass M_c in the composite

$$\frac{dM_c}{dt} = -\rho_c A V_c = -\rho_c A S_c \int_0^{h_c} \mu_c dz \quad (10)$$

where ρ_c is the resin density, A is the cross sectional area of the prepreg parallel to the tool plate h_c is the thickness of the resin-starved layer, i.e. the thickness of the layer through which resin flow takes place (Fig. 4). P_u is the pressure at the interface between the prepreg and the bleeder. The subscript c refers to conditions in the prepreg at position h_c . Accordingly, P_c is the pressure at h_c and is taken here to be approximately the same as the applied pressure ($P_c \sim P_o$).

At any instant of time the flow rate out of the prepreg is equal to the flow rate into the bleeder

$$\rho_c A V_c = \rho_b A V_b \quad (11)$$

The temperature, and hence, the viscosity, of the resin inside the bleeder is assumed to be independent of position (but not of time). Thus eqs. (9) and (11) yield

$$\rho_c A V_c = \rho_b A \frac{S_b}{\mu_b} \frac{P_u - P_b}{h_b} \quad (12)$$

where h_b is the instantaneous depth of resin in the bleeder. The subscript b refers to conditions in the bleeder. In developing the above expressions the pressure drop across the porous teflon between the bleeder and the prepreg was neglected.

The resin densities are taken to be constant ($\rho = \rho_c$). With this approximation eqs. (10) - (12) may be rearranged to yield the following expression for the resin volume flow rate

$$\frac{dV_r}{dt} = \frac{-AS_c}{\int_0^{h_c} \mu_c dz} \left(\frac{P_o - P_b}{1 + G(t)} \right) \quad (13)$$

$G(t)$ is a parameter defined as

$$G(t) = \frac{S_c}{S_b} \frac{\mu_b h_b}{\int_0^{h_c} \mu_c dz} \quad (14)$$

V_r is the resin volume in the composite at any instant of time. The volume of resin that left the prepreg and entered the bleeder in time t is

$$V_{rT} = \int_0^t \frac{dV_r}{dt} dt \quad (15)$$

The volume of resin remaining in the composite is

$$V_r = V_{ri} - V_{rT} \quad (16)$$

and the composite resin volume fraction at time t is

$$v_r = \frac{V_r}{V_r + V_f} \quad (17)$$

where V_{ri} is the initial ($t=0$) resin volume in the prepreg and V_f is the fiber volume.

The instantaneous resin depth in the bleeder is related to the resin flow rate by the expression

$$h_b = \frac{1}{m_b A} \int_0^t \frac{dV_r}{dt} dt \quad (18)$$

m_b is the porosity of the bleeder and represents the volume (per unit volume) which can be filled by resin. The thickness of the resin-starved layer is

$$h_c = nh_1 \quad (19)$$

h_1 is the thickness of one ply and n is the number of plies in the resin-starved layer

$$n = V_{rT}/V_a \quad (20)$$

where V_a represents the volume in each ply from which resin can be removed. Thus V_a is the difference between the initial resin volume in the ply and some minimum volume from which the resin can never be squeezed out. The value of V_a can be estimated from the known initial prepreg geometry. The parameter n must be an integer, such that $n = 1$ when $V_{rT} < V_a$, $n = 2$ when $V_{rT} < 2V_a$ and so on.

Equations (10) through (20) are the relationships needed for calculating the resin flow.

VOID MODEL

The size of a void in the cured composite is influenced by the shape, size, and location of the void nucleus in the prepreg at the start of the cure. Unfortunately, these parameters are unknown, precluding the possibility of determining accurately the void distribution and void sizes in the cured composite. However, an approximate relationship between void size and the cure temperature and cure pressure can be established. This relationship can then be used to estimate the rate of change in void size when the initial location and initial size of the void nucleus are known.

In the analysis a spherical nucleus of diameter d_1 is assumed to be at a given location in the prepreg. The nucleus is filled with water vapor resulting from the humid air surrounding the prepreg during lay-up. The partial pressure of the water vapor in the nucleus PP_{wi} is related to the relative humidity ϕ by the expression

$$PP_{wi} = \phi P_{wg} \quad (21)$$

where P_{wg} is the saturation pressure of the water vapor at the ambient temperature. From the known values of the initial partial pressure PP_{wi} and the ini-

tial nucleus volume. The initial mass m_{w1} and the initial concentration $(c_{vw})_1$ of the water vapor in the nucleus can be determined.

During the cure the volume of the void changes because a) water and other types of molecules are transported across the void-prepreg interface, and b) the cure pressure increases the pressure at the location of the void. For a spherical void of diameter d , the total pressure inside the void P_v is related to the pressure in the prepreg surrounding the void P by the expression

$$P_v - P = \frac{4\sigma}{d} \quad (22)$$

σ is the surface tension between the resin and the void. The total pressure is the sum of the partial pressures of the air and the different types of vapors present in the void.

$$P_v = \sum_j PP_j \quad (23)$$

where PP_j is the partial pressure of the j -th species. The partial pressure in the void due to the j -th species is a known function of the temperature T , the mass of the species inside the void m_j , and the void diameter d

$$PP_j = f_j(T, m_j, d) \quad (24)$$

Thus, if the pressure in the prepreg around the void, the temperature inside the void (taken to be the same as the temperature of the prepreg at the void location), and the mass of vapor in the void are known, the partial pressure, the total pressure and the void diameter can be calculated from eqs. (22) - (24). The temperature and the pressure are given by the thermo-chemical-flow-model. It remains to evaluate the mass of each type of vapor in the void as a function of time. The change in vapor mass may be calculated by assuming that the vapor molecules are transported through the prepreg by Fickian diffusion (27). For each type of vapor (denoted by the subscript j) Fick's law gives (28)

$$\frac{\partial c_j}{\partial t} = D_j \left(\frac{\partial^2 c_j}{\partial R^2} + \frac{2}{R} \frac{\partial c_j}{\partial R} \right) \quad (25)$$

c_j is the concentration of the j -th vapor at a radial coordinate R , with $R=0$ at the center of the void. D_j is the diffusivity of the j -th vapor through the prepreg in the R direction.

Initially ($t < 0$) each type of vapor is taken to be distributed uniformly in the prepreg and has the known concentration $(c_j)_1$. The void contains only water vapor at the known concentration $(c_{vw})_1$. The initial conditions corresponding to eq. (25) may be written as

$$\left. \begin{array}{ll} c_j = (c_{vw})_1 & \text{at } R < d_1/2 \\ c_j = (c_j)_1 & \text{at } R \geq d_1/2 \end{array} \right\} t < 0 \quad (26)$$

At times $t > 0$ the vapor concentration at the void-prepreg interface must be specified. By denoting the concentrations at the prepreg surface by the subscript m , we write

$$\left. \begin{array}{ll} c_j = (c_m)_j & \text{at } R = d/2 \\ c_j = (c_j)_1 & \text{at } R \rightarrow \infty \end{array} \right\} t \geq 0 \quad (27)$$

The second of the above expressions reflects the fact that the concentration remains unchanged at a distance far from the void. The surface concentration is related to the maximum saturation level M of the particular vapor in the prepreg (27, 29).

$$(c_m)_j = \rho_j M_j \quad (28)$$

when ρ_j is the vapor density. The value of M can be determined experimentally for each vapor-prepreg system (30).

Solutions of eqs. (25) - (28) yield the vapor concentration as a function of position and time $c_j = f(R, t)$. The mass of vapor j transported in time t through the surface^j of the void is

$$m_{jT} = - \int_0^t \pi d^2 D_j \left[\frac{\partial c_j}{\partial R} \right]_{R=d/2} dt \quad (29)$$

The mass of the j -th vapor in the void at time t is

$$m_j = (m_j)_i - m_{jT} \quad (30)$$

The initial mass of water vapor in the void is known, as was discussed previously. For all other types of vapor (except air) $(m_j)_i$ is equal to zero.

Solution to eqs. (21) - (30) give the void size as a function of time. It is emphasized again that the solution requires a knowledge of the initial size and location of the void. The solution also requires a knowledge of the vapors which are released from the prepreg during the cure. This latter information may not be available. In this case, the calculation can only be performed with the assumption that only water vapor is transported through the void-prepreg interface. This assumption does not affect the formulation of the model but it simplifies the calculation procedure.

STRESS MODEL

The procedure for calculating the residual stresses can be found in texts such as Tsai and Hahn (31) and Jones (32). The development presented here is along the line given by Tsai and Hahn. Only the outlines of the calculation procedure are included here. For details the reader is referred to reference (31).

As a starting point, we consider a [0/90] laminate cooled from the cure temperature to room temperature T_a (Fig. 5). If the two plies were unconnected the 0 degree ply would deform by e_1 and the 90 degree ply would deform by e_2 . Furthermore, the plies would be stress free. In practice the two plies are connected and the deformation of both plies is the same e_0 . The subscript zero indicates that the strain across the laminate thickness is constant. This strain gives rise to the residual stresses in the 0 and 90 degree plies. This specific example may now be generalized to a symmetric laminate with arbitrary ply orientation. For such a laminate the residual stress in any given ply is

$$\sigma_i = Q_{ij} (e_{0j} - e_j) \quad (31)$$

Q_{ij} is the modulus as defined by Tsai and Hahn (31). The relationship between Q_{ij} and the engineering constants can be found in ref. (31). The strain e_{ij} may be computed from the expression

Figure 5: Illustration of the buildup of residual stresses after curing (31).

$$e_j = \alpha_j (T_e - T_a) \quad (32)$$

where T is the temperature in the ply under consideration at the end of the cure and T_a is the ambient temperature. The value of T_e is provided by the thermo-chemical model. α_j is the thermal expansion coefficient. The laminate curing strain e_{oj} is

$$e_{oj} = a_{ij} \int_0^L Q_{ij} e_j dz \quad (33)$$

z is the coordinate perpendicular to the plane of the laminate. a_{ij} is the in-plane compliance of a symmetric laminate as defined by Tsai and Hahn.

Equations (31)-(33) comprise the equations needed for calculating the residual stresses in each ply.

METHOD OF SOLUTION

Solutions to the model described in the foregoing must be obtained by numerical means. A computer code suitable for generating numerical results was developed at The University of Michigan. With this code (designated as CURE) the solution proceeds along the following major steps

- 1) The input parameters are specified.
- 2) The temperature, the degree of cure, and the resin viscosity are calculated as functions of position and time.
- 3) The thickness of the resin starved layer, the resin volume fraction in the composite, and the instantaneous depth of resin in the bleeder are calculated.
- 4) The void sizes are calculated.
- 5) The residual stresses in each ply and the laminate curing strain are calculated.

The computer code can be used to establish the appropriate cure cycle. To accomplish this the calculations are performed for different cure cycles until the desired results (outputs) are obtained.

The computer code may also be employed in controlling the cure temperature and cure pressure during manufacture. Signals from sensors (e.g. thermocouples) located in the laminate are fed into a microprocessor. These signals are compared with the values of the corresponding parameters calculated by the computer code. On the basis of these comparisons the microprocessor transmits the required control signals to the heaters and the pressure regulators.

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